

Effect of *Moringa Oleifera* Dried Leaves on Lipid Profile of Albino Rats

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of oral administration of *Moringa oleifera* (MO) leaves on serum lipids in diet induced hyperlipidemia rats. Proximate analysis was carried out to ascertain the composition of the diet used. The mean protein content of *Moringa oleifera* (MO) and Cholesterol Rich Diet (CRD) showed significant increase but the protein content of CRD+5% MO & CRD+10% MO showed no significant increase. The mean crude fat of CRD with 5%, 7.5% and 10% (MO) showed significant decrease compared with the CRD, this implies probable increase in cholesterol levels. Thirty-five albino rats were used in this experiment. They were divided into five groups. The first group was fed on basal diet as control. The second group was fed on high fat diet (2% cholesterol) to induce hyperlipidemia as a positive control. The third, fourth and fifth groups were fed on high fat diet containing 5%, 7.5% & 10% MO powder respectively. The effect of oral administration of MO leaves on serum lipids were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0. The results shows that the high cholesterol/ fat diet feeding for 35 days resulted in a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in cholesterol level and a decrease in levels of triacylglycerides, High density lipoprotein (HDL), Very Low Density Lipoprotein (VLDL) and Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL) (Group II). The mean serum HDL -cholesterol of normal control rats (Group I) was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared with negative control rats (Group II). The mean HDL -cholesterol of animals fed with 10% (Group V) was significantly higher compared with animals fed with 7.5% cholesterol (Group IV). The triacylglycerides level of animals fed with 5% (Group III), 7.5% (Group IV) and 10% (Group V) all showed significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease compared to animals fed with cholesterol rich diet. The study indicated that *Moringa oleifera* reduces serum lipids, its consumption can be encouraged to lower serum lipid levels.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, diet, Lipid profile, Albino rats, oral administration

Introduction

Healing with medicinal plants is as old as mankind. Awareness of medicinal plants usage is as a result of the many years of struggles against illnesses due to which man learned to pursue drugs in barks, seeds, fruit bodies and other parts of the plants. Advances in science and technology exemplified by improved separation and purification techniques have significantly aided scientific investigations of the efficacy of many therapeutic natural products (Colon, Al-Ghaferi, Abraham and Leprince, 2007). At the time there was no sufficient information either concerning the reasons

for the illnesses or concerning which plant and how it could be utilized as a cure. Everything was based on observation and personal experience. One of the medicinal plants which could have antilipidemic effects is *Moringa oleifera* (Moringaceae) commonly known as drumstick tree. The leaves are reported to have antihypertensive, hypocholesterolemia, antiulcer, antiatherosclerotic and normal healing activities (Dangi, Jolly and Narayanan, (2002), Ghasi, Nwobodo and Ofili (2000), Pal, Mukherjee and Saha (2006) and Chumarka, Sanvarinda, Phornchirasilp, Morales, Phivthong-

Ngam, Ratana, Chamnong, Srisawat, and Pongrapeeporn, (2008)). The hypolipidemic activity of its fruits was also reported by Mehta, Balaraman, Amin, Bafna and Gulati, 2003.

Moringa leaves contain bioactive phytoconstituent (β -sitosterol) with cholesterol lowering effect. This compound is capable to reduce cholesterol level from the serum of high fat diet. Lipid and lipoprotein abnormalities are regarded as highly modifiable risk factors for cardiovascular disease (Ghasi, et al., 2000). Lipid profiles are commonly used in the routine evaluation of cardiovascular risk, given the high correlations of hyperlipidemia and cardiovascular risk. A standard lipid profile includes determination of serum or plasma total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein-associated cholesterol (HDL-C), low-density lipoprotein-associated cholesterol (LDL-C), and total triglycerides (TG). Albino rats are perfect research specimen because of their similarity to humans. They are mammals and are shown to have genetic, biological and behavioral similarities with humans. As such, they are used in research for cancer, human psychology, hormonal issues, and even obesity. Although there have been several reports on the cholesterol reducing effect of the aqueous and ethanol leaf extracts of *M. oleifera* in rats, there is still paucity of information on the hypolipidaemic activity of the dried leaves at the doses investigated in the present study. Considering the use of *M. oleifera* for the treatment of various ailments, there is the need to investigate the possible effect of the plant on some biochemical parameters as it relates to weight and lipid in animals. In this study, we therefore present information on the hypolipidemic effect of dried leaves of *Moringa oleifera* on the serum lipid profile using experimentally

induced hyperlipidemic wistar (albino) rats as model.

Materials and methods

Materials

Fresh *Moringa oleifera* leaves were obtained from Madarkaci area in Zaria Local Government, Kaduna State. They were Shade -dried, pulverized and sieved to pass through 0.5mm mesh size. The leaves were taken to Botany Department, Bayero University, Kano for identification. Albino rats of either sex were obtained from Department of Pharmacology and clinical pharmacy, Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) Zaria. The rats were maintained on starter feeds (produced by vital feeds Nigeria limited) and water. The animals were housed in animal house of Biological Sciences Department, Bayero University Kano in polypropylene cages at room temperature throughout the study.

Preparation of cholesterol -rich diet

The cholesterol -rich diet was formulated according to the model described by Vesselinvitch et al., (1980): Pure cholesterol (2%) and palm oil (20%) were thoroughly mixed with grower mash feeds.

Experimental animals

Thirty five (35) albino rats were used as experimental animals. The animals randomly distributed into five groups of seven rats each:

Group I rats were fed basal diet without cholesterol and plant supplement.

Group II were fed with cholesterol -rich diet but no plant supplement

Group III were fed with cholesterol -rich diet plus 5% *Moringa oleifera* leaves.

Group IV were fed with cholesterol -rich diet plus 7.5% *Moringa oleifera* leaves.

Group V were fed with cholesterol -rich diet plus 10% *Moringa oleifera* leaves.

The Methods of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 1990) was used for proximate analysis of formulated feeds. Determination of ash content was done by ashing at 550°C for 3h. The Kjeldahl method was used to determine the protein content. The crude fiber content of the samples was determined by digestion method and the fat was done by Soxhlet extraction method. At the end of five weeks feeding period, the rats were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and blood was collected from the heart into a plain tube. The serum was prepared by centrifugation of blood samples at 3000rpm for 15 minutes. The serum was used in the estimation of lipid profile (Total cholesterol, VLDL, HDL-cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol and triacylglycerides). The triacylglycerides was determined after enzymatic hydrolysis and oxidation (CHOD -PAP) by colorimetric method (Jacobs and Von Demark, 1960). The high density lipoproteins (HDL) cholesterol was determined using enzymatic (CHOD-PAP) method (Lopes-Virella et al., 1977). The low density lipoprotein (LDL) -cholesterol concentration was determined using Friedewald formula (Friedewald et al., 1972). The total cholesterol concentration was determined using (CHOD -PAP) colorimetric method (Allain et al., 1974).

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out with the use of (SPSS) version 16.0 software. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to separate the mean and the level of significance used was 5 % ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results

Figure 1 presents the nutrient composition of feeds fed to rats. The mean protein content of *Moringa oleifera* (MO)

and Cholesterol Rich Diet (CRD) showed significant increase but the protein content of CRD+5% MO & CRD+10% MO showed no significant increase. The mean crude fat of CRD was significantly higher when compared with the basal diet ($p \leq 0.05$). The mean crude fat of CRD with 5%, 7.5% and 10% (MO) showed significant decrease compared with the CRD, this implies probable increase in cholesterol levels. Furthermore comparing the carbohydrate content of CRD+10% MO was significantly higher when compare with basal diet.

Table 1 presents the result of serum lipid profile of rats after feeding of various doses of dried powdered *Moringa oleifera* (MO) leaves 5%, 7.5%, 10% for a period of 35 days. The high cholesterol/fat diet feeding for 35 days resulted in a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in cholesterol level and a decrease in levels of triacylglycerides, HDL, VLDL and LDL (Group II) when compared to the normal control experimental rats. For the cholesterol, significant reduction was seen profoundly in rats administered the 10% *M. oleifera* leaves. The mean serum HDL -cholesterol of normal control rats (Group I) was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared with negative control rats (Group II). The mean HDL -cholesterol of animals fed with 10% (Group V) was significantly higher compared with animals fed with 7.5% cholesterol (Group IV). The triacylglycerides level of animals fed with 5% (Group III), 7.5% (Group IV) and 10% (Group V) all showed significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease compared to animals fed with cholesterol rich diet. Furthermore comparing the mean serum LDL cholesterol of positive control (Group I) and negative control (Group II) showed no significant decrease. Animals fed with 5% (Group III) and 7.5% (Group V) showed significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease compared

with animal fed with basal diet (Group I). Moreover, the mean serum VLDL - cholesterol of animals fed with cholesterol rich diet (Group II) showed significant decrease when compared with animals fed

with 7.5% and 10%. There was no significant difference when the VLDL - cholesterol of rats in Group III and Group V were compared.

Figure 1: Nutrient Profile of Feeds Fed to Rats

Values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). "a" indicated significant difference ($P < 0.05$) when compared with "M. oleifera leaves (MOL)" feed. "b" indicated significant difference ($P < 0.05$) when compared with "Basal Diet" feed. "c" indicated significant difference ($P < 0.05$)

when compared with "Cholesterol-Rich Diet (CRD)" feed. "d" indicated significant difference ($P < 0.05$) when compared with "CRD + 5% MOL" feed. "e" indicated significant difference ($P < 0.05$) when compared with "CRD + 7.5% MOL" feed.

Table 1: Lipid Profile of Rats after Oral Administration of Various Dosages of Dried Powdered *Moringa oleifera* for a Period of 35 Days.

Groups	Cholesterol (mmol/L)	TG (mmol/L)	HDL (mmol/L)	VLDL (mmol/L)	LDL (mmol)
I	4.08 \pm 0.14 ^{abcd}	1.32 \pm 0.02 ^{abcd}	2.38 \pm 0.04 ^{abcd}	1.57 \pm 0.80 ^{abcd}	3.59 \pm 0.15 ^{abcd}
II	4.8 \pm 0.5 ^{ae}	2.53 \pm 0.03 ^{ae fg}	0.60 \pm 0.02 ^{ae fg}	0.88 \pm 0.28 ^{ae f}	3.38 \pm 0.69 ^{de f}
III	4.86 \pm 0.04 ^{bf g}	1.91 \pm 0.01 ^{be hi}	2.17 \pm 0.12 ^{be hi}	0.45 \pm 0.33 ^{be g}	2.24 \pm 0.31 ^{ad gh}
IV	4.81 \pm 0.01 ^{cf h}	1.56 \pm 0.05 ^{cf hj}	2.30 \pm 0.01 ^{cf hj}	0.73 \pm 0.04 ^{cf gh}	1.77 \pm 0.03 ^{be ig}
V	3.90 \pm 0.07 ^{de gh}	0.93 \pm 0.07 ^{de ij}	2.51 \pm 0.01 ^{de ij}	0.42 \pm 0.03 ^{df h}	0.97 \pm 0.03 ^{cf hi}

The values are represented as mean \pm standard deviation (mean \pm SD). Values in the same column with similar superscripts are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ compared with the control.

Discussion

Alteration in the concentration of major lipids like serum total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and triacylglycerides (TAG) could give useful information on the lipid metabolism as well as predisposition of the heart to atherosclerosis and its associated coronary heart diseases (Yakubu, Akanji, and Oladiji, 2008). There was significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the levels of serum cholesterol, triacylglycerides and LDL-C and a decrease in level of HDL-C in the high fat diet fed animals (Group II) when compared to those fed with normal diet (Group I) (Table 1). Elevated level of blood cholesterol especially LDL-C is known major risk factor for CHD whereas HDL-C is cardio protective (Gonzales and Rodriguez, 2001). A rise in cholesterol and TG has been associated with Coronary heart disease (CHD) (Oyedepo, Babarinde and Ajayeoba, 2000). The increase in cholesterol in this case may have been as a result of formation of adrenocortical and sex hormones (Patil, Prakash and Maheshwari, 2010). Increased TG could cause the liver to form other types of lipids particularly the phospholipids (Patil *et al.*, 2010).

There was a significant decrease in serum total cholesterol ($p < 0.05$) observed (Table 1), this may be due to decrease in the concentration of acetyl CoA arising probably from reduced β -oxidation of fatty acid, since acetyl-CoA is a key substrate in the biosynthesis of cholesterol (Rang, Dale and Ritter, 1995). Low blood cholesterol concentration is one of the

important beneficial factors that do not predispose an individual to cardiovascular diseases (Treasure, Klein, Weintraub, Talley, Stillabow, Kisonki, Zhang, Boccuzzi, Codarholm and Alexander, 1995). Plant sterols inhibit the absorption of dietary cholesterol but the resulting decrease in serum cholesterol has been slight. *M. oleifera* has been reported to contain β -sitosterol in HPTLC. β -sitosterol is a plant sterol with a structure similar to that of cholesterol, except for the substitution of an ethyl group at C24 of its side chain (Dubey, Dora, Kumar, and Gulsan, 2013). The cholesterol lowering effect may be due to this inhibition in reabsorption of cholesterol from endogenous sources in association with a simultaneous increase in its excretion into faeces in the form of neutral steroids. Chlorogenic acid and moriginine are constituents of *Moringa oleifera* and they reduce serum total cholesterol (Cho, Jeon, and Kim, 2010).

Treatment with *Moringa oleifera* leaves at three different doses significantly decreased the level of total TG and cholesterol as compared to the controls (Table 1) which could be due to increased activity of extrahepatic lipase (Ithagarasi and Shyamala, 1997), which is responsible for the circulation of lipoprotein in a non-atherogenic direction by efficient lipolysis of triglyceride rich lipoprotein in heart, skeletal muscle and adipose tissue (Shimada, Shibashi, Inaba, Yagyu, Harada, Osuga, Ohahi, Yazaki and Yamada, 1996, Zsigmond, Kobayashi, Tzung Kwifuke, and Cham 1977; Yaghu, Ishibashi, Chen, Osuga, Okazaki, Perrey, Kitamin, Shimada, Ohash, Harak, Shionoin, Yahab, Gotoda, Yazak and Yamada, 1999). Triacylglycerols are the main storage form of fatty acids. The decrease in serum triacylglycerides may be due to reduced lipolysis. This may

deplete the store of fatty acids. Also, reduced serum triacylglycerol (TAG) level in the treated animals could be correlated to elevated lipoprotein lipase which is in agreement with previous studies (Phil-Sun, Sei-Jung and Kye-Taek 2006, Kannel, Castelli Gordon and Mcnamara 1971) on mushroom extracted exo-biopolymer.

In the present study, administration of Moringa at 10%, which showed significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in serum HDL-C when compared to the control animals is beneficial, and 'may' not predispose the animals to cardiovascular risk. Clinically, increased HDL is beneficial to health since it reduces the risk of coronary heart disease (CHD) (Phil-Sun *et al.*, 2006). High density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) is considered to have anti-atherogenic properties. It has also been shown that increase in HDL-C correlates inversely with coronary heart disease (Mayes, Murray, Granner and Rodwell, 1996).

LDL-C is known to be the primary marker for a number of degenerative diseases, particularly arteriosclerosis. LDL-C carries cholesterol from the liver to the blood stream. Therefore, when LDL-C is reduced, the amount of cholesterol being carried will also reduce (Rana, Nieuwdorsp, Jukma, and Kastelein, 2007). For low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), it is known that for being effective antihyperlipidemic agent, the compound should reduce the plasma levels of LDL-C as it transport 70% of plasma cholesterol in humans (Phil-Sun *et al.*, 2006). Epidemiological and clinical studies have demonstrated positive correlation in LDL-C concentration in serum and risk of coronary heart diseases (Bordia and Verma, 1998). Overall, the study showed that there was reduced

level of all lipids except the HDL-C, and this may be beneficial to the animal as this pattern of alterations are associated with reduced risk of atherosclerosis and its coronary heart diseases. Therefore, such decrease in the serum lipid contents may be beneficial to the animals as it may not enhance obesity, atherosclerosis and hypertension (Enas, 1999). These findings have similarities with the work of other researchers (Mona, Eman and Aya 2013, Denen, Ejike, Moses, Seriki, and Chiamaka, 2014).

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study showed that *M. oleifera* has hypolipidaemic effect in rats. This is an indication that the leaves of *M. oleifera* can be used in lowering lipid levels and possible complications of cardiovascular diseases.

The dried powdered leaves of *M.oleifera* may be recommended to patients having abnormal high lipid profile levels, individuals that are obese or those that want to maintain body weight.

References

- Allain, C.C., Poon I.S., Richmond, C.H.G. & Fu, P.P. (1974). Enzymatic Determination of Cholesterol. *Clinical Chemistry*, 20, 470-471
- AOAC, (1997). Methods of Analysis of Association of Official Analytical Chemists (16th Ed) Washington, D.C.1, 600-792.
- Bordia, A. & Verma, S.K. (1998). Effect of *Celastrus Paniculatus* Wild Oil (Bravobol) on Blood Lipids in Patients of Coronary Disease. *Antiseptic*, 95(4), 112
- Cho, A.S., Jeon, S.M. & Kim, M.J. (2010). Chlorogenic Acid and Moriginine Exhibit Anti-Obesity Property and Improves Lipid Metabolism in High-Fat Diet-Induced-Obese Mice. *Food*

- and *Chemical Toxicology*, 48(3), 937-943.
- Chumarka, P., Sanvarinda, Y., Phornchirasilp, S., Morales, N., Phivthong-Ngam, L., RatanaChamnong, P., Srisawat, S. & Pongrapeeporn, K. (2008). The in Vitro and Ex Vivo Antioxidant properties Hypolipidemic and Antiatherosclerotic Activities of water extract of *Moringa Oleifera* Lam Leaves. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 50, 1-8.
- Colon, J.M., Al-Ghaferi, N., Abraham, B. & Leprince, J. (2007). Strategies for Development of naturally occurring Antimicrobial Peptides into Therapeutically Valuable Anti-Infective Agents. *Volume Methods*, 42(4), 349-355.
- Dangi, S. Y., Jolly, C. I. & Narayanan, S. (2002). Antihypertensive Activity of the Total Alkaloids from the Leaves of *Moringa Oleifera*. *J. pharmaceutical Biol*, 40 (2), 144- 148.
- Denen, A., Ejike D. E., Moses D.A., Seriki, S.A. & Chiamaka N.U. (2004). Hypolipidaemic Effect of Ethanol Leaf Extract of *Moringa Oleifera* Lam. In Experimentally Induced Hypercholesterolaemic Wistar Rats. *Int. J. Nutr. Food Sci*. 3, 355-360.
- Dubey, D., Dora J., Kumar, A. & Gulsan, R. (2013). A. Multipurpose Tree – *Moringa Oleifera*. *International Journal of pharmaceutical and Chemical Sciences*, 2 (1), 2277- 2282.
- Enas, E.A. (1999). Cholesterol made Easy: The Good, Bad and The Ugly. (Cadi Research, USA).
- Friedwald, W.T., Levy, R.I. & Fedrickson, D.S. (1972). Estimation of the Concentration of Low Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol in Plasma without use of the preparative Ultracentrifuge. *Chemist*, 18 (6), 499-515.
- Ghasi, S., Nwobodo, E. & Ofili, J.O. (2000). Hypocholesterolaemic Effect of Crude Extract of Leaf of *Moringa oleifera* Lam in High Fat Diet Wistar Rats. *Journal Ethnopharmacology*, 69, 21-25.
- Gonzalez –Castejon, M. & Rodriguez –Casado, A. (2001). Dietary Phytochemicals the Potential effects on Obesity: A Review. *Pharmacological Research Journal*, 64 (5), 438-55.
- Ithagarasi, A.P. & Shyamala, D. C.S. (1997). Effect of α –Tocopherol on Isoproterenol induced Changes in Lipid and Lipoprotein Profile in Rats. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 29, 399-404.
- Jacob, N.J. & Vondemark, P.J. (1960). Enzymatic Determination of serum Triglyceride. *Biochemica Biophysical Research*, 88, 250-255.
- Kannel, W.B., Castelli, C.W., Gordon, T. & Mcnamara, P.M. (1971). Serum Cholesterol, Lipoprotein and the Risk of Coronary heart Diseases. *Annals of International Medicine*, 36, 74:1
- Mehta, K., Balaraman, R., Amin, A.H., Bafna, P.A. & Gulati, O.D. (2003). Effects of Fruits of *Moringa oleifera* on the Lipid Profile of Normal and Hypercholesterolaemic Rabbits. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 86, 191-195.
- Mona S.H., Eman M. E. & Aya A.A. (2013). Effect of *Moringa oleifera* on Serum Lipids and Kidney Function of Hyperlipidemic rats. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 9(8), 5189 - 5198.
- Oyedepo, T.A., Babarinde, S.O. & Ajayeoba, T.A. (2000). Evaluation of

- Anti-Hyperlipidemic Effect of Aqueous Leaves Extract of *Moringa oleifera* in Alloxan Induced Diabetic Rats. *International Journal of Biochemistry Research & Review*, 3 (3), 162-170.
- Pal, S.K., Mukherjee, P.K. & Saha, B.P. (2006). Studies on the Antiulcer Activity of *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Extract on Gastric Ulcer Model in Rats. *Phytotherapy Research*, 44, 898-901.
- Patil, R.H., Prakash, K. & Maheshwari, V.L. (2010). Hypolipidemic Effect of *Celastrus Paniculatus* in Experimentally Induced Hypercholesterolemic Wistar Rats. *Indian Journal of Clinical Biochemistry*, 25 (4), 405-410.
- Phil-Sun, O., Sei-Jung, L. & Kye-Taek, L. (2006). Hypolipidemic and Antiobeditive of the Plant Glycoprotein (36 KDA) From the *Rhus Vernicifulia* Stokes Fruit in Triton Wr-1339 Induced Hyperlipidemic Rats. *Bioscience Biotechnology and Biochemistry*, 70 (2), 44-100.
- Rana, J.S., Nieuwdorsp, M., Jukma, J.W. & Kastelein, J.J. (2007). Cardiovascular Metabolic Syndrome –An Interplay of Obesity, Inflammation, Diabetes and Coronary Heart Disease. *Diabetes Obesity Metabolism*, 9, 218-232.
- Rang, A.P., Dale, M.M. & Ritter, J.M. (1995). Pharmacology (3rd Edition). *Churchill Livingstone* (p.409). New York.
- Shimada, M., Shibashi, S., Inaba T., Yagyu, H., Harada, K., Osuga, J., Ohahi, K., Yazaki, V. & Yamada, N. (1996). Suppression of Diet -Induced Atherosclerosis in Low Density lipoprotein Receptor Knockout Mice over Expressing Lipoprotein Lipase. *Proceedings of National Academy science USA*, 93, 7242-7246.
- Treasure, C.B., Klein J.L., Weintraub, W.S., Talley, J.D., Stillabow, M.E., Kisonki, A.S., Zhang, B., Boccuzzi, S.J., Codarholm, J.C. & Alexander, R.W. (1995). Beneficial Effects of Cholesterol Lowering Therapy on the Coronary Heart Disease. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 332, 481.
- Vesselinitch, D., Wissle, R.W., Schniffner, T.T. & Borenaztajn, I. (1980). The Effect of Various Diets on Atherogenesis in Rhesus Monkey. *Atherosclerosis*, 35, 189-207.
- Yaghu, H., Ishibashi, S., Chen, Z., Osuga, J., Okazaki, M., Perrey, S., Kitamin, T., Shimada, M., Ohash, K., Harak, K., Shionoin, F., Yahab, N., Gotoda, T., Yazak, Y. & Yamada, N. (1999). Over Expressed Lipoprotein Lipase Protects Against Atherosclerosis in Apolipoprotein E Knockout Mice. *Journal of Lipid Research*, 40, 1677-1685.
- Yakubu, M. T., Akanji, M.A. & Oladiji, A.T. (2008). Alterations in Serum Lipid Profile of Male Rats by Oral Administration of Aqueous Extract of *Fadogia Argrestis* Stem. *Journal of Medical Plant Research*, 2, 66.
- Zsigmond, E., Kobayashi, K., Tzung Kwfuke, Y. & Cham, L. (1977). Adenovirus Mediated Gene Transfer of Human Lipoprotein Lipase Ameliorates the Hyperlipidemias Associated With Apolipoprotein E and LDL Receptor Deficiencies in Mice. *Human Gene Therapy*, 8, 1921-1933.